

MEDICAL AWARENESS IN THE FIELD OF HEALTH CARE IS THE BASIS OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF THE POPULATION

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Medical awareness in the field of health is an important condition for maintaining and promoting health. Prevention and a healthy lifestyle are considered together as a factor in ensuring public health. This necessitates a scientific substantiation of systemic measures to increase the level of medical awareness, medical, social and preventive activity.

The aim of the study: To study organizational and preventive measures to promote health and improve the quality of life based on the formation of a competent, integrated approach to the health of urban and regional residents.

Materials and methods of research: 62 residents of the city of Tashkent and 59 residents of the Tashkent region over 20 years old took part in the study. A medical and sociological study was conducted on medical awareness, preventive activities, health and quality of life of the population. Cluster analysis was used to divide the population into groups according to the level of medical awareness. As indicators, questions were used regarding awareness of the state of health and risk factors for diseases, as well as questions assessing the presence of competence in the field of conditions and methods of disease prevention, basic measures and types of activities to improve one's own health.

Results: Among the Tashkent city (68.7%) and Tashkent region (84.8%) residents, women predominated. In the age structure of city residents, the largest share belongs to residents 21-28 years old (55.3%). About a third of the regional residents were 38-57 years old (27.9%), more than a third were 20-28 years old (34.3%). Among urban residents, people with higher (45.1%) or secondary specialized education (44.9%) predominated. More than half of the surveyed rural residents (57.1%) had specialized secondary education, 42.1% had higher education. Using cluster analysis, city and regional residents were divided into groups according to the level of medical awareness. Less than half of urban residents had a high level of medical awareness (48.7%), 37.5% had an average level, and 16.9% had a low level of medical awareness. Persons with a high level of medical awareness had comprehensive knowledge about the state of their health, had a personal understanding of the importance of regular

medical examinations, and had a sufficient level of knowledge on maintaining a healthy lifestyle. On the contrary, people with a low level of medical awareness in most cases had no idea about the state of their health, generally did not undergo regular medical examinations, and knew practically nothing about the factors influencing health.

Conclusions: Primary medical knowledge, skills and abilities should mainly be instilled by parents. The level of medical awareness directly affects the health indicators and quality of life of the urban and regional population, which determines the population's need to obtain a higher level of knowledge, skills and abilities in individual healthcare. Insufficient medical awareness and unsatisfactory commitment to healthcare initiate the risk of deterioration in the health and quality of life of urban and regional residents, which indicates the priority importance of the information and educational impact of medical workers in the process of developing medical knowledge, starting from the period of preschool education and ending with the period of health protection during active professional and labor activity.

References:

1. R.V. Mukhacheva. Quality of life as a scientific category: theoretical approaches to determining. A. V. Mukhacheva Vestnik KemSU 2012 No. 4 (52). 303.
2. G.P. Teske. Managing the quality of life of the region's population based on its assessment and forecasting. Bulletin of Chelyabinsk State University. No. 2 (484) (2024):
3. A.V. Lyadova. A healthy lifestyle as a value: the view of young people. Medical news. 2016. 33-38
4. A.V. Zelionko. Medical awareness as a key competency in developing a healthy lifestyle among urban residents. International scientific research journal. 2014. T.21. No. 2-3. 71-73.
5. M.V. Avdeeva, Yu.V. Lobzin, V.S. Luchkevich. The relevance of improving the prevention of chronic non-communicable diseases in the primary health care system. Doctor. 2013. No. 11. 83-85.
6. S.A. Alynin. Healthy lifestyle propaganda in educational organizations. Pedagogical Journal. 1-2`2015. 47-53

